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GEO-STUDIES FORUM

An International Journal of Environmental and Policy Issues

**Department of Geography and Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Sciences,
University of Ilorin, Nigeria**

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Address: Department of Geography & Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Science, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.

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ANALYSIS OF FLOOD DISASTER RISK AND EXPOSURE IN THE COMMUNITIES OF KIRI DAM'S CATCHMENT, ADAMAWA STATE, NIGERIA

Ikusemoran Mayomi, Department of Geography, University of Maiduguri
Mukthar Alhaji, Department of Geography, University of Maiduguri
Sambo Rita, Department of Urban and Regional Planning, Ramat Polytechnic, Maiduguri

Abstract: *Kiri reservoir with the sole aim of providing water for irrigating the savannah sugar plantation at the downstream of the reservoir was impounded in 1982. Since 2012, the flooding in the area has resulted into annual disaster. Therefore, this study focused on the analysis of flood disaster risk among the communities within the catchment of the reservoir. Three communities; Banjiram (Guyuk LGA) from the western side of the reservoir, Gombiyel (Shelleng LGA) at the eastern side and Bare (Numan LGA) at the downstream were purposively sampled for the assessment and analysis of flood disaster risk. Disaster Risk Management Systems Approach which comprises risk (hazard identification and elements at risk) and vulnerability analysis (physical and socio-economic vulnerability) was adapted for the analysis of disaster risk in the catchment. The topography of the communities was generated in ArcGIS 10.7.1 environment, while proximity of each of the communities were also mapped. Each of the structures in the three communities were captured (using Global Positioning System) and overlaid on to generated terrain maps. Combination of GIS technique and administration of structured questionnaires which consists of the actual locations of individual building, house structures, flood occurrence/frequency/exposure, natural and social economic environments were used to generate data for the analysis of flood disaster risk in the catchment. The results revealed that among the three sampled communities, Banjiram community was less exposed to disaster risk while Gombiyel was most exposed. Furthermore, the elements at risk and exposure in the three communities showed that all the communities have close proximity to the Reservoir but house structures are generally poor in the catchment and therefore need to be strengthened by encouraging the inhabitants to erect houses with good foundation and corrugated roof so as to reduce the vulnerability of the houses to flood and improve their resilience. Among the recommendations are: prompt dissemination of information on flood early warning system in the local languages of the people and also implementation of land allocations and landuse practices in all the communities along the reservoir and the valley of River Gongola so as to minimize indiscriminate building of houses within very vulnerable areas to flood.*

Keywords: Kiri Reservoir, Elements at Risk, Flood Disaster Risk, Hazard Identification, Flood Vulnerability, Capacity Assessment

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

The rapid increase in population in Nigeria and the need to provide the basic necessities for human use have made the government at all levels to embark on developmental projects in all sectors like industrial, agricultural, transportation and education. Kiri reservoir, at the downstream of River Gongola was constructed out of the necessity to make provisions for irrigation of sugarcane plantation which provides the principal raw material for the Dangote Sugar Refinery PLC, Numan, Adamawa State (then a Federal Government project known as Savannah Sugar Company). According to United Nations Environmental Programme [UNEP], (2007), in spite all the benefits derived from dams by the communities of their domains, the dams often cause havoc to the riparian communities. Vuno and Shende (2015) stated that dams have negatively affected more than 60% of the world's rivers and have displaced between 40-80 million people globally. Hydrological hazards and disasters are extreme events associated with water: based on the occurrence, movement, and distribution. Geo-hydrological hazards are major threats to human life, property, cultural heritage and the natural and built environments (Loukas, *et al.*, 2021). Okada, *et al.*, (2007) opined that disasters resulting from exposure to hazards have been on increase in the past fifty years and that water disaster has accounted to about 10-30% of the economic losses from disasters, and therefore, concluded that, 50-100% of the total losses from water disasters are caused by flood disaster.

Disasters are defined by the United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Risk Reduction [UN-ISDR], 2004; World Confederation for

Physical Therapy [WCPT], (2016) as “a serious disruption of the functioning of a community or a society causing widespread human, material, economic or environmental losses which exceed the ability of the affected community or society to cope using its own resources”. In the summary of Smith (1996) in Stephen (2018) “a disaster generally results from the interaction, in time and space, between the physical exposure to a hazardous process and a vulnerable human population”. The International Decade of Natural Disaster Reduction (IDNDR) in Schneiderbauer & Daniele (2004); Frazer *et al.*, (2016) emphasized the ‘risk triangle’ and the dependency of risk on the three components of hazard, exposure and vulnerability. The risk triangle showed that risk is at the center of hazard, vulnerability and exposure. Vulnerability is people’s ability to cope with a particular hazard in an area. Therefore, Frazer *et al.*, (2016) explained that Disaster risk analysis is the center of the procedures of Disaster Risk Management (DRM) because generated information from risk analysis is used to estimate the risk of individuals, populations, property or the environment to various hazards. Vulnerability assessments and risk analyses allow for the identification of areas of critical concern and help to guide mitigation efforts. According to Komolafe, *et al.*, (2015), hazards occurrences do not necessarily lead to disaster until there are vulnerable exposed elements.

The recent rapid frequency of flood disaster specifically since 2012 within Kiri dam’s catchment have necessitated the studies of flood disaster risk reduction and management. During the reconnaissance survey for this research, it was discovered that the environs of Kiri reservoir have severally

been affected by some environmental disasters especially floods, which has resulted into loss of lives, and displacement of several people (Adamawa State Emergency Management Agency (ADSEMA, 2015). The existing and proposed projects on the dam, the presence of Dadin Kowa dam at the upstream that might soon be fully in operation, as well as the frequent occurrence of hydrological hazards and disaster, all call for the need to assess hydrological hazards and existing or potential disaster risk in the catchment. Therefore, because of the high impacts of hydrological hazards on the economy, man and environment, reliable methods such as geospatial technique for the assessment of disaster risk as carried out in this study is imperative.

THE STUDY AREA

The reservoir's catchment is a sub-catchment of the entire Gongola basin. Kiri reservoir was constructed by the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN) between 1976 and 1982 under the management of the Upper Benue River Basin Development Authority (UBRBDA). Guyuk and Shelleng are the two riparian LGAs to Kiri reservoir. It was constructed mainly to supply water for irrigating over 6,000 hectares of sugarcane estate of the SSCL (Shallangwa *et al.*, 2014, Zira *et al.*, 2015). The reservoir is located between latitudes 9° 40' 37.14" and 9° 53' 36.85"N of the equator, and longitudes 11° 58' 41.13" and 12° 03' 20.27"E of

the Meridian (Fig. 1). The dam's catchment covers major parts of Guyuk and Shelleng LGAs and some parts of Demsa, Numan and Song LGAs. The catchment also extends beyond Adamawa State into the Lunguda mountains in Balanga LGA of Gombe State (Fig. 1).

Rivers Aworolok which is also known as River Hombe is the main river at the north-eastern side of the catchment, while River Wuro Yanka which is the largest river in the entire catchment drains the southern part of Shelleng and some parts of Demsa, Numan and Song LGAs. At the western side of the catchment which is mainly covered with limestone rocks are few streams which include Guyuk, Sukwaraha and Kwadaddai which all drain into the reservoir. Kiri reservoir area has a tropical climate with dry and wet seasons. The wet season starts from April and ends in October while the dry season begins in November and ends in April. The average rainfall of the area is between 700 and 800 mm per annum with July to September as the wettest months. Kiri reservoir area has an average temperature of 26.1-27°C in December to January and maximum between 33-38°C in April to May (Emmanuel, 2016, Zemba *et al.*, 2016). The vegetation of the study area lies within the Southern Guinea Savannah with patches of few types of woodland mainly trees with shrubs and tall grasses (Akosim *et al.*, 2020).

Figure 1. The Study Area.

Source: Extracted from ASTERDEM V2 (2011); Digitized by Ikusemoran (2022)

METHODOLOGY

SAMPLING OF COMMUNITIES AND ADMINISTRATION OF QUESTIONNAIRE

Three communities were purposively sampled; one each at both sides of the dam's catchment, that is, Banjiram, in Guyuk LGA side and Gombiyel in Shelleng LGA side of the dam's catchment. The third is Bare in Numan LGA at the downstream of the reservoir. The samples were based on the frequency, intensity and extent of floods which was obtained during the reconnaissance studies that were carried out between 1st and 2nd of August 2020, 4th and 5th of March 2021 and 8-9th July, 2021. All the houses and their attributes in each of the three sampled settlements were selected for the study so that the heterogeneous topography of each of the communities would be properly examined. The attribute data of each of the houses in the communities were generated through the administration of questionnaire.

STEPS IN DISASTER RISK MAPPING

Risk analysis generally contains the following steps: hazard identification, hazard assessment, elements-at-risk/exposure analysis, vulnerability assessment and risk estimation.

DISASTER RISK MAPPING

The structures and the facilities such as schools, health centers like clinics, dispensaries, places of worships (Churches and Mosques), police posts, and other buildings at risk in the area were all captured using GPS. The locations of the structures were overlaid on the terrain of the communities so as to enable clear assessment of the structures in flood vulnerable areas based on the terrain. Buffer zones of each of the communities from the main water bodies were also generated for proximity assessment. Finally, the degree of flood risks was classified into four:

highly severe, severe, marginally severe and safe zones while different colors applied to indicate the degree of flood risks.

VULNERABILITY AND CAPACITY ASSESSMENT (VCA)

VCA were conducted to generate more information especially on some social-cultural effects of flood disaster that might be difficult to obtain through remotely sensed data and GIS techniques. Three communities (Banjiram, Gombiyel and Bare) were purposively sampled (based on the frequency, intensity and extent of floods which was obtained during the reconnaissance studies for the study; one each at both sides of the dam's catchment. The VCA members in each community comprised of: (i) community head or representative (ii) one male health officer, (iii) one female health officer, (iv) youth leader (v) one religion leader, (vi) women leader (vii) a farmer (viii) one fisherman (ix) an educational officer and (ix) a transporter.

DATA ANALYSIS

The obtained data from the questionnaire were analyzed in tabular forms, while hazards and proximity maps were digitally generated using Geographical Information System methods.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

HAZARD IDENTIFICATION

From field observations and reports from VCA, soil erosion and flood hazards were the main meteorological hazards that were identified within the catchment. However, only floods have resulted into disaster in the catchment, having displaced temporarily or permanently some people, destroyed so many structures and means of livelihood and most importantly has led to loss of many lives. For instance, in 2012 an estimated number of more than thirty people were swept away by flood in Bare community in Numan LGA in their sleep. In 2018, an

eight-year-old girl while sleeping in her house was killed by flood in Banjiram community in Guyuk LGA. In 2020, two people in a boat were also said to have been carried away on their way back from their farms on River Gonggola in Bare community. All these facts were obtained from the conducted VCA which have also been captured by Ikusemoran, (2022).

HAZARD ASSESSMENT

Hazard risk maps of the three sampled communities were shown in Figs 2, 3 and 4. The hazard maps showed the physical structures within the community like residential, public facilities (education, health, commercial and others) as well as water points. Table 1 shows the components of the hazard maps in each of the three sampled communities.

Figure 2. Flood hazard map of Banjiram

Figure 3. Flood hazard map of Bare community

Source: Authors field survey and mapping (2022) Source: Authors field survey and mapping (2022)

Fig. 4. Flood hazard map of Gombiyel community
Source: Authors field survey and mapping (2022)

Table 1. Components of the hazard maps

Features/Facilities	Banjiram	Bare	Gombiyel
Buildings	There were seven hundred and ninety-six (796) houses, out of which sixteen (16) were public buildings while the remaining seven hundred and eighty (780) buildings were residential.	Bare community contains five hundred and thirty-nine (539) houses, fourteen (14) of them were public buildings and the other ones were residential.	The community comprises of two hundred and seventy-nine (279) houses among which eight (8) were public buildings while the remaining were residential.
House Population	The residential buildings contain three thousand, eight hundred and eighty-one (3,881) persons which is an average of five (5) people per house.	The 539 houses contain three thousand, five hundred and ninety eight (3598) people constituting an average of seven (7) people per house.	These 279 houses contain two thousand one hundred and seventeen (2,117) people, that is, an average of eight (8) persons per house.
Age Structure	Out of the 3.881 people, eight hundred and seventy-one (871) which is 22.44% were children within ages 0-5, while two hundred and eighty-six (286), that is, 7.73% were aged people above 65 years. Therefore, the under aged and the aged in the Banjiram community constitutes 29.81% of the total inhabitants.	From the 3,598 people, eight hundred and fifty-four were children within 0-5 years (23.74%) and two hundred and seventy-one (271) people (7.53%) were aged people above 65 years. Collectively, one thousand, one hundred and twenty-five (1,125) people constituting 31.27% of the total population were children and aged people which might be too high to manage during flood disaster because it reduces self-rescue capacity during disaster.	Out of the 2,117 population, five hundred and forty-six (546) were within ages 0-5 and one hundred and five (105) were aged people above 65 years. Cumulatively, six hundred and fifty (650) people which is 30.70% are either children or aged. The high percentage of children and aged reduces self-rescue capability during flood disaster.
Water Points	Due to the limestone nature of the geology of the community, water accessibility has been a serious problem (VCA), Hence, only four water points are available in the large community. That is, one borehole and three wells.	Bare community has the highest public and commercial facilities with fourteen (14) structures as well as the highest water points, that is, seven (7) boreholes (though that of the MDG was not functioning as at the time of the study) and six wells.	Gombiyel community has seven (7) water points (3 boreholes, 3 wells and the stream separating the community from Gwagarab village.

Source: Authors field survey (2022)

VULNERABILITY AND EXPOSURE TO FLOOD IN BANJIRAM COMMUNITY

Banjiram community is dissected by two streams: the larger Kwasalda and the narrower Kwamajule at the northern and southern parts of the community respectively (Figs. 2 & 4). These two streams are seasonal, but frequently cause flood disaster within the community which has also been noted by Bulus, (2014). Field observation revealed that about 100 m buffer along Kwasalda streams and 50 m buffer along Kwamajule streams are frequently most vulnerable to flooding as shown in Fig. 5. Along the 100 m buffer zone of Kwasalda stream in the north are one hundred and thirty-two (132) houses containing six hundred and sixty-nine (669) people (red arrows in Fig 5), while the 50 m buffer zone of the narrow Kwamajule stream in the south contains twenty-seven houses which are abodes for two hundred and seventeen (217) people. These figures show that 22.83% of the inhabitants are exposed to flooding from the two streams. The vulnerability and exposure to flood in Banjiram community are presented in Table 2

VULNERABILITY AND EXPOSURE TO FLOOD IN IN BARE COMMUNITY

Though, Bare community has close proximity to River Gongola (less than 1km buffer), but most of the houses (78.66%) and people (82.52%) are located on higher terrain which limits the adverse impact of flood disaster in the community (Fig. 3). Most public facilities like education (primary school), health (PHC) and water points (3 wells and 2 out of the 3 boreholes were located in low or moderately low terrains which are frequently subjected to floods (Fig. 3) The lesson learnt from the sad event of flood disaster in Bare community in 2012 when more than 35 people submerged in water in their deep sleep in the night, educated the inhabitants of the community on the best sites for their residential houses. As at 2022, only 24 (with 174 people) and 73 (with 710 people) houses were located in low terrain and moderately low terrain respectively and which

are highly prone to flood hazards (Fig.3). Collectively therefore, ninety-seven (97) houses (34.77%) with eight hundred and eighty-four (884) people (41.77%) were found in very low terrain areas. The remaining one hundred and eighty-two (182) houses (65.23%) and one thousand, two hundred and thirty-three (1233) people (58.24%) were living on higher terrain in order to minimize the devastating flood effect on the community (Ikusemoran, 2022). The vulnerability and exposure to flood in Bare community are presented in Table 2.

FLOOD VULNERABILITY AND DISASTER RISK IN GOMBIYEL COMMUNITY

Gombiyel community is the smallest in terms of the number of houses and population among the three sampled settlements. It comprises two hundred and seventy-nine (279) houses among which eight were public buildings while the remaining were residential (Fig. 4). The 279 houses contained two thousand one hundred and seventeen (2,117) people, that is, an average of eight persons per house. Out of the 2,117 population, five hundred and forty-six (546) were within ages 0-5 and one hundred and five (105) were aged people above 65 years. Cumulatively, six hundred and fifty (650) people which is 30.70% are either children or aged (Ikusemoran, 2022). The community has eight public facilities comprising of religious centers, shops for commercial purposes, educational institutions and religious centers. The community also has seven (7) water points (3 boreholes, 3 wells and the stream separating the community and Gwagarab. The vulnerability and exposure to flood in Gombiyel are presented in Table 2.

Figure 5. Flood risk buffer zones along the two streams in Banjiram

Source: Authors survey and mapping (2022)

Table 2. Flood vulnerability and exposure in Banjiram, Bare and Gombiyel Communities

S/N	Elements	Banjiram Community	Bare Community	Gombiyel Community
1	Housing			
	House Age	About 78.64% of the houses in Banjiram community are old (above 15 years) which can easily collapse during flood disaster	About 69.52% of the houses in Bare community are above 15 years which were considered old enough to collapse during flood due to the poor nature of most of the structures	75.72% of the houses in Gombiyel are more than 15 years old and therefore, at risk to flood disaster
	House Floor	59.80% of the houses were not floored and the floor were also not raised to prevent water from entering the houses which makes such houses to be at risk during flood disaster	About 47.61% of the houses in Bare community were not floored or raised	59.42% of the houses in Gombiyel community have their floors not raised or floored and hence, exposed to flood risk
	House Roof	About 37.31% of the houses in Banjiram were made of thatched roof which cannot withstand flood	55.18% of the roofs of Bare houses were made up of thatched roof	38.41% of the roofs of the houses in the community were made up of thatched roof which also expose them to flood risk
	House Foundation	Only 10.55% of the housing structures in Banjiram had no foundation which means the risk of houses without foundation is low in the community	Higher percentage of 47.01% of the houses in Bare community has no foundation	Gombiyel has the highest percentage of 55.43% of the houses without foundation among the three sampled communities. Coupled with their low terrain and proximity to the dam, the community is at great risk to flood
	House Walls	More than half (52.51%) of the houses in Banjiram community were made up of mud and not plastered which put such houses at great flood risk	High percentage of 58.37% of the walls of the houses in Bare community were made up of mud and not plastered	52.54% of the walls of the houses in Gombiyel were mud and not plastered which exposed them to flood risk.

Source:

Authors field survey (2022)

2 Topography

Terrain	Though, cumulatively, 66.21% of Banjiram houses are located in extremely (low floodplains) and highly (moderately low floodplains) which subject the houses to flood risk, but generally the community is located on higher terrain with the least elevation at 193.8 m which is higher than the highest elevations of Bare (159.1m) and Gombiyel (184 m).	The elevation of Bare community ranges from 151.4 to 159.1 m above sea level. This general low terrain of the area subjects all the houses in the community to flood disaster	Gombiyel is located on elevation between 179.7 to 184 m above sea level. This relatively low topography of the community makes all the structures in the community to be at risk to flood.
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Distance from Dam/River	Two hundred and twenty-one (221) houses (27.76%) were within 3 kms buffer, while the remaining five hundred and seventy-five (575) houses constituting 72.24% of the total houses in the community are located beyond 3 kms buffer	All the houses in Bare community were located within 1 km buffer zone from River Gongola. This close proximity to the river immediately at the downstream of Kiri reservoir makes the area to be prone to flood disaster	Although none of the houses in the community is located within 0-1km buffer from Kiri reservoir, but 178 out of the 279 houses (65.44%) which contains 1,336 people, that is, 63.11% of the total population, were located within 1-2 kms.
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3 Public Facilities

Health Centers	The only health center in the community (PHC) is located on higher terrain (moderately high floodplains) which reduces its risk to flood disaster	The PHC which is the only health facility in the community is though located on higher ground if the terrain of the community is considered, but the elevation of the place is too low to cub flood hazard	The PHC which is the only health center in the community was not only located on moderately low flood plains but was also within 1-2 km buffer distance from the dam which put the center at great flood risk
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Source: Authors field survey (2022)

Table 2 (ctd). Flood vulnerability and exposure in Banjiram, Bare and Gombiyel Communities

Education	While the only primary school is located on moderately high terrain which makes it to be at less risk to flood, the only secondary school (GSS) is located on moderately low terrain which subjects the school to frequent flood and which has made parts of the school buildings to frequently collapse as shown in Plate 7.3a	The two primary schools in the community are located in a moderately low terrain which makes the two schools to be subjected to flood hazards to the extent that sometime the schools have to close for some days because of inaccessibility to the schools due to flood.	It is also very unfortunate that the only primary school which is also one of the government establishments was located within 1-2 km buffer distance from the dam and also on very low terrain which also exposes the school.
Religious	Except African Church, all other churches in the community (Baptist, LCCN, Catholic, Deeper Life, Gesthmani among others) are located in either low or moderately low terrain, while the two Mosques in the community are located on higher terrain which makes them to be less at risk to flood	Except Charismatic Church which is located on moderately terrain, all other churches (Catholic, LCCN, and Deeper Life) are all located on higher ground and therefore, less prone to flood hazard	All the religious centers (all the Mosques, Baptist and LCCN churches) are located on higher terrain and hence, at less risk to flood
Water Points	The only borehole in the community is located on moderately low terrain creating inaccessibility to the borehole during the rainy season as the inhabitants has to arrange stones and sandbags to access the borehole. Though the three wells are located on higher terrain but are unfortunately located along the streams which subjects the three wells to flood disaster as the wells were said to sometimes fill to the mouth or even overflow during the rainy season (VCA findings)	From the seven available boreholes in the community, the four that are located in the core of the community are on high elevation (Fig.4). However, the remaining three that are found at the southern part of the community including the MDG borehole (which was not functioning at the time of the study) were all found in moderately low terrain which subject them to flood risk facilities	Only one out of the three boreholes were located on higher terrain, the remaining two are located on moderately low floodplains. The three wells are also at risk to flood disaster because all of them are located in moderately and low flood plains

Source: Authors field survey (2022)

Table 2 (ctd). Flood vulnerability and exposure in Banjiram, Bare and Gombiyel Communities

4	Roads	The 2.7 kms length of the main road within the community is located in low or moderately low terrain which makes some parts of the road to be filled with water during flood and poses problems to the road users.	While almost all the roads from Catholic Church northwards are located on higher elevation, those from the church towards the south are found on low terrain areas. Out of the total length of 6.28 km roads that were mapped, 2.95 kms were found in low terrain and at risk to flood disaster.	Out of the 0.49 km length of the main road within the community, 0.32 km length are located on moderately low and low floodplains which mean substantial length of the road within the community are at risk of flood disaster
5	Land Exposure	1.20 and 1.22 Sq km of the land in the mapped Banjiram community are located within low and moderately low terrain respectively which collectively constitute 50.42% of the total land of the mapped area. Farmlands on these areas are at risk and frequently subjected to floods.	All the land areas in the community are exposed to flood hazards because of their general low terrain (151.4-159.1) and close proximity to River Gongola which was the main factors to the 2012 mass flood disaster in the community.	57.89% of the community falls within 1-2 km buffer zone form the dam. Moreover, moderately low and low terrain covers 0.21 and 0.30 Sq. km respectively. Hence, 53.68% of the land areas are within moderately low and low floodplains. The community is almost enclosed by large streams which also expose the entire community to flood disaster
6	Income	About 31.04% of the total households of the community receive less than N100, 000 per annum which means many people are financially exposed to flood hazard.	29% of the total households in the community receive less than N100,000 per annum, less people are financially at risk to flood than Banjiram community.	24.03% of the total households in the community receive less than N100,000 per annum, less people are financially at risk to flood among the three communities
7	Crop lost by flood	15.59% of the households in the community losses more than N100,000 values of crops due to flood disaster	Higher percentage of 56.2% losses more than N100,000 values of crops to flood disaster due to the low terrain and close proximity to R.Gongola	Highest percentage of 76.34% losses more than N100,000 values of crops to flood disaster among the three communities

Source: Authors field survey (2022)

8	House Damage	Based on the number of times houses have damaged by floods, 10.54% of the houses in Banjiram have damaged more than twice due to floods	A very low percentage of 4.6% of the houses in the community have damaged more than twice due to stringent conformity to site for residential building since the 2012 flood massacre.	5.81% of the houses in Gombiyel have been damaged by flood more than twice. Due to the fact that most of the inhabitants have identified where not to build their houses and strictly adhere to it.
9	Values of damaged houses	36.06% of the houses in the community which has been damaged by floods has gulped more than N 100, 000	Due to less damaged houses, a less percentage of 25.8% of the total damaged houses has consumed more than N100, 000.	46.12% of the damaged houses have taken more than N100,000 to repair, the highest among the three com

Table 2 (ctd). Flood vulnerability and exposure in Banjiram, Bare and Gombiyel Communities

Source: Authors field survey (2022)

Table 3. Elements at Risk in Kiri Dam’s Catchment Communities

Vulnerability Classes		Communities/Roads
Highly Vulnerable Areas	LGAs	
	Guyuk	Communities: Chikila, Dangir, Gugu, Gunda, Gundeyi, Guyuk. Roads: 17.94 kms length of main road, 5.49 kms length of secondary roads, 52.28 kms length of minor roads. Educational Institutions: 8 Primary Schools in Chikila, Gwalura, Guyuk town, Sili Kasa, Lamsa Kasa, Gugu, Gwana and Dangir 2 Secondary Schools at Lamsa Kasa and Chikila. Health: Chikila PHC. Security: Police Station and Police Barracks Guyuk. Religious: LCCN, Chikila
	Shelleng	Communities: Bakla, Gelode, Gwambia, Kambilam, Gwagarab, Gombiyel, Ladenu, Mitim, Shembulu, Wuro Yanka, Lakati, Wari. Roads: 16.66 kms length of secondary roads, 86.99 kms length of minor roads. Educational Institutions: 3 Primary Schools (Kola, Tallum and Gwararap), 4 Secondary Schools located in Shelleng, Gwagarap, Tallum and Kiri town. Water: 1 borehole in Shelleng. Security: Police Station and Barracks at Shelleng, Civil Defence also in Shelleng. Commercial: Weekly Market and Cattle Market, Shelleng
	Demsa	Communities: Kofa Fada, Labua, Sabewa, Wuro Munchi. Roads: 4.79 kms length of minor roads. Health: Kofa Fada Clinic
	Numan	Communities: Bare, Bilachi, Ndasso. Roads: 9.87 kms length of minor roads. Education Institutions: 3 Primary Schools in Bilachi. Ndasso and Bare. Health: 2 Health Centers, that is, Bare PHC and Kofa Clinic
Vulnerable Areas	Guyuk	Communities: Banjiram, Pondiwe, Jiu, Hinjira. Roads: 8.76 kms length of main road, 0.09 kms length of secondary roads, 51.84 kms length of minor roads. Education Institutions: 2 primary schools in Guyuk, 1 each in Dangir, Pondiwe, Jiu, Gundeyi, Lakumna and Hinjari. 3 Secondary Schools in Guyuk and one in each of the following villages: Banjiram, Jiu and Lamza Kasa. Health: General Hosp. Guyuk, PHC Guyuk and PHC in Falu, and Banjiram. Water: 2 boreholes in Guyuk. Communication: MTN, Glo, 9 Mobile and Airtel masts all in Guyuk. Security: Civil Defense and Immigration Service at Guyuk. Administrative: Area and Magistrate courts at Guyuk. Commercial: Weekly Market at Guyuk
	Shelleng	Communities: Shelleng, Mabonde, Shindiwi, Bakta, Dingi, Jonkolo and Libau. Educational Institutions: 1 primary school in Shelleng and Baktar, 1 Secondary school in Shelleng and. Baktar. Roads: 9.62 kms length of secondary roads, 38.38 kms length of minor roads Health: PHC Baktar and Kiri. Water: 1 Borehole at Shelleng.
	Demsa	Communications: MTN, 9 Mobile and Airtel masts at Kiri. Administrative: Magistrate court, Shelleng
		Communities: Libari, Roads: 4.83 kms length of minor roads
	Numan	Communities: Nill. Roads: 2.33 kms length of secondary road,

Source: Authors field survey (2022)

ELEMENTS AT RISK AND EXPOSURE

The facilities (private or public), population and economic values exposed to any form of hazards in an area are collectively referred to as elements at risk (UN-ISDR, 2004). The degree at which the elements at risk are located in vulnerable area is generally referred to as exposure. The elements at risk and exposure are presented in Table 3.

CONCLUSION

Geospatial techniques have been discovered to be the most effective and reliable means of acquisition and analysis of spatial data which are integrated with attribute data for flood disaster monitoring and management as revealed in this study. The rural areas of the study are still neglected in terms of growth and development, higher percentages of the inhabitants are living in thatched roof houses, mud houses without plaster, many with no house foundation and thereby exposing the communities to flood disaster. The result of the hazard risk maps of the communities showed that Banjiram was less exposed, while Gombiyel was more exposed to flood disaster risk among the sampled communities. The vulnerability and exposure analysis in the three communities revealed that house structures are generally poor in the catchment and therefore need to be strengthened by encouraging the inhabitants to erect houses with good foundation and corrugated roof so as to reduce the vulnerability of the houses to flood and improve their resilience

RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1 Implementation of land allocations and landuse practices in all the communities along the reservoir and the valley of River Gongola so as to minimize indiscriminate building of houses within very vulnerable areas

to flood. Construction of public facilities in safer zone areas such as higher terrain or areas far away from water bodies to minimize submergence of the facilities during flood disaster.

- 2 Creation of door-door awareness on environmental issues and regular/prompt provisions of flood early warning systems in the local languages of the inhabitants to educate the people on disaster risk reduction.
- 3 Involvement of the community in making decisions on sensitive environmental issues in the communities such as landuse planning and utilization or flood risk management. This will bring out better decisions based on the knowledge and experiences of the inhabitants in the small communities.

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